

After AlphaFold2 - A status quo and its relevancy for drug discovery.

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ABSTRACT

In 2021 DeepMind released AlphaFold2 which is an AI system being able to predict 3D-structures of nearly all catalogued proteins. This review mainly summarizes the achievements of AlphaFold2, its relevancy in the drug discovery process, and explores its advantages and limitations.

KEYWORDS

AlphaFold, Drug Discovery, Artificial Intelligence, Drug Development, Protein structure prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2021 DeepMind released AlphaFold2, a neural network based model, which delivers a solution to a grand challenge in both structural biology and artificial intelligence (AI) – the prediction of three-dimensional protein structures. [1]

Proteins are essential building blocks of life. The function of proteins is depending on its fold and structure, which creates high interest in the exact 3D shapes of proteins. [2] The problem of predicting protein structures is a question of how a one-dimensional protein sequence of amino acids results in a three-dimensional structure. [3]

Since this question has high relevancy for many research areas a contest on solving the protein structure prediction problem is held every second year – the contest of the Critical Assessment of Protein Structure Prediction (CASP). [4]

In 2020 groundbreaking achievements were realized during CASP14 by DeepMind, a London-based company - the release of an AI tool called AlphaFold2. [5] For the first time in history with AlphaFold2 it was possible to predict 3D structure folds of proteins achieving accuracy levels which are comparable to experimental methods. [6] This sensation was welcomed by scientists and proclaimed as a revolution for structural biology with high impact to many research areas just like drug discovery. [7]

Now, nearly two years after the release of AlphaFold2 – I would like to review on the impact of AlphaFold2 for the field of drug discovery.

II. ACHIEVEMENTS

When AlphaFold2 was taking part in the CASP14 competition it greatly outperformed other protein structure prediction tools. [8] The competitions measurement of prediction accuracy is the Global Distance Test (GDT). AlphaFold2 achieved a median GDT score of 92.4 (out of 100) and 87.0 on the free modelling-category of proteins. [2] The next best performing methods scored with 72.8 and 61.0 in the respective categories. [9]

This level of accuracy is comparable to experimental techniques of protein structure determination like X-ray crystallography and considered as a breakthrough in solving the protein fold prediction problem. [7]

Figure 1: AlphaFolds breakthrough [8]

The accuracy of fold predictions is variable (both within and between models) and depending on the protein. Whilst prediction accuracies for single-chain, structured proteins are remarkably good – the quality of predictions can differ from a proteins length and flexibility.[3]

Therefore AlphaFolds predictions also include confidence estimates where each model is superimposed and assessed on experimentally determined structures (if available). [4]

Figure 2: Accuracy indications for AlphaFold2 predictions [4]

In July 2021 DeepMind released next to the source code of AlphaFold2 roughly one million 3D protein structures and published these to a public database. [10] Only one year later in August 2022 further protein folds were published for nearly all catalogued proteins known to science. This release expanded the database to an extend of 200 million structures for humans, plants, bacteria, animals and other organisms. [11]

The predictions of AlphaFold2 have greatly increased the knowledge of protein structures not only for the human genome but also for other species. A majority of confidently known structures is only generated by AlphaFold2. [4]

Figure 3: Source of knowledge about proteomes [4]

According to DeepMind the protein fold database was in twelve months accessed by over half million researchers from over 190 countries which already shows the high interest in AlphaFold2 by the scientific community. [11]

Further the company published two papers about AlphaFold2 which also enjoy high interest. This can be measured by looking at the number of citations and research articles over time. To date the paper describing AlphaFold2 was cited more than 4900 times.

Figure 4: Popularity of AlphaFold2 in research community [4]

Since the CASP14 competition in 2021 AlphaFold2 has become omnipresent in the field of protein fold prediction. Also the latest contest CASP15 in late 2022 showed that the most successful approaches of protein fold prediction incorporated AlphaFold2. [5].

III. LIMITATIONS

Even though AlphaFold2 is proclaimed as a solution to the grand challenge of the protein folding problem the program also has its limitations.

There are structural limitations which keep researchers from using AlphaFold2. The program uses vast computational resources which are hardly accessible and reproducible for many researchers. [2] Further there is the necessity of simplification of the AlphaFold2 code (without losing accuracy). This would enable researchers to modify the program to specific research questions in the domain of interest. [2]

As shown in Figure 2 AlphaFold's protein structure predictions are not of equal accuracy. Some predictions can be considered as just a starting point in case of weak prediction qualities. Since there is a lack of experimental data which could be used for verification, the benefit of inaccurate predictions can differ (if not vanish) depending on the field of research. [3]

IV. RELEVANCY OF ALPHAFOLD IN DRUG DISCOVERY

The function of a protein in a cell is determined by its structure. [6] And over the last decades exactly this lack of precise 3D structures was the bottleneck in drug discovery. [7]

The misfolding of proteins can cause diseases which can be inhibited if a drug molecule could precisely

dock on the protein. An accurate knowledge of the structures and folds of proteins is therefore highly relevant in the field of drug discovery. [2]

Precise knowledge about the exact shape of a protein enables both, the identification of hit molecules and the evaluation of the druggability of a disease. [6]

Before AlphaFold2 protein structures were determined in cost and time extensive experiments. Nowadays AlphaFold2 and AI in general are extensively employed in various drug discovery stages with the advantages of high efficiency, fast speed, and low cost. [12]

Although protein structures solely do not lead to new drugs immediately, they surely are crucial knowledge towards the understanding of how proteins work and how a modulation of proteins might lead to a disease or a therapy. [3]

V. STATUS QUO OF ALPHAFOLD2 IN DRUG DISCOVERY

With the reveal of millions of protein folds utilizing AlphaFold2 roughly two years ago also new possibilities for the field of drug discovery were created. The industry can already report some achievements as well as limitations by using AlphaFold2.

Scientists report that AlphaFold2 is already used even before the drug discovery phase with the assessment of druggability of a target protein. For drug discovery it is important to know to which extend proteins have pockets or grooves allowing small molecule compounds to bind. This helps researchers to estimate which targets are a major challenge and which ones are possible to target. This knowledge provided by AlphaFolds 3D-structures lead to improved prioritization of targets and delivers massive time savings. [13]

Further there have been successes by using AlphaFold structures in virtual screens and compound design for drug candidates. With the usage of additional software to determine fine details of amino-acid side chains or locations where individual hydrogen atoms might sit, AlphaFold structures have in some cases proved good enough to guide drug discovery. [4]

Moreover some scientist already are synthesizing potential drugs identified by using AlphaFold2 structures, and testing their activity in the lab. [4]

AlphaFold2 creates great possibilities by improving the drug discovery and the development process by making it faster and more cost-effective. However, there is also the need for good-quality data to produce meaningful results. [14]

Scientists are concerned that current accuracy levels of the predicted protein structures, especially in

active and allosteric pocket areas, are not yet reliable. [2] So, AlphaFolds predictions can sometimes just be seen as an initial approximation that can be validated or refined by an experiment – and which itself helps to make sense of experimental data. [4]

Experiments linked to early breast cancer, further have shown that AlphaFold2 is not capable to predict the effect of protein mutations. [15] Mutations disrupt a protein's natural structure with effects to their shape. AlphaFold2 further was not trained to determine how proteins change shape in the presence of other interacting proteins, or molecules such as drugs. [4]

Surely, there is still some progress to be made when predicting protein folds. Nevertheless, AlphaFold2 is a sensation which already is omnipresent in the field of drug discovery. In future AlphaFold2 is considered to be helpful when accurately designing and discovering better and safer drugs that could successfully treat or cure people. [13]

VI. OUTLOOK

Since John Moult, a computational biologist and founder of CASP, in 2020 proclaimed the protein folding prediction problem as somehow solved with AlphaFold2– will there still be the necessity for big improvements in this area of research?

The answer is yes. In recent CASP15 competition some further challenges have already been incorporated in the contest. AlphaFold2 was not designed to determine how proteins interact with other molecules such as drugs. It is also relevant to know how mutations can alter a proteins structure. Both challenges have emerged as a result from the success of AlphaFold2. Nevertheless, this knowledge is necessary to improve AI based drug discovery in future. [5]

The legacy of Alphafold2 is incredible, and making big improvements to AlphaFold2 will take time and require new innovations in machine learning and protein structure prediction. However, there are already different applications tested: Some methods – including one developed by Meta – use language models, such as those used in predictive-text tools. These models did not outperform AlphaFold2 in CASP15 but can deliver new potentials. [5]

Since scientists proclaim the 3D predictions of AlphaFold2 as too vague and unreliable also the prediction accuracies of AlphaFold2 must be further tested and improved. [4]

Anyway, AlphaFold2 is considered as a game changer and increases the pace of experiments in this field frenetic. [4] AlphaFold2 is also not only an

innovation but the solution to the grand challenge of structural biology: the 3D protein fold prediction with increasing impact to drug discovery. [1]

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